

CHAPTER 1

1 Introduction

Materials science encompasses researchers from different collaborative fields, these researchers design new materials, study their structure and properties, modulate these properties and develop novel synthesizing and characterizing techniques. With the advancement in research techniques, social development happens from hunter-gatherers to modern societies. This progress to a large extent has been made possible by controlling the composition and dimensions of state-of-the-art materials. The development in the 'techno-industrial sector', the backbone of modern societies is directly linked with advancement in material science and processing techniques in designing novel materials. It is being acknowledged that consistent effort is needed to synthesize new multifunctional materials and modulate their properties for futuristic applications. The stages in material selection to device fabrication can be represented as Material processing → Characterization → Properties → Applications → Device Fabrication.

Searching of new material with promising characteristic to solve the energy issue is at new heights. At the beginning of modernization, experimentation was the unique way for the advancement in material science, led by empirical and theoretical rules. However, with the beginning of computer simulation, things got changed. Machine-learning and effectual simulations thereby make inroads into materials science [1-3]. The main theme of computational physics is to solve long-standing problems with computer simulations in the physical and chemical world [4-6]. Although theory for these problems may exist, however, the resulting mathematical equations are intractable by the analytical approach, so computer simulation comes to the rescue. Computer simulations describe real systems using mathematical models [7]. The validation of numerical models depends upon the

precision of output results and at what price those results are delivered [8]. The validated model turns into a predictor that enhances scientific understanding by providing information that may not be accessed experimentally or theoretically. This enrichment paves the way for further experimental and theoretical research, which in turn will affect numerical modeling. This signifies the three research axes are not contradictory but complementary [9]. Therefore, in the present era, besides the experimental synthesis, numerical modeling based on density functional theory (DFT) has emerged as a predictive tool to design new materials. This research area is comparatively new and still developing consistently because of computation power and algorithmic improvements [10].

The formula of development in society by designing new novel materials holds to foresee the future: building the world of tomorrow requires new advanced smart materials. Within the material science discipline, there are a plethora of different research problems that could prove to be gamechangers for the technological revolution. The hot research topics in the current scenario are green energy generation and storage including solar cells, thermoelectric, hydrogen energy, lithium-ion batteries, supercapacitors; high-temperature superconductivity; nano-structuring: quantum dots, graphene; material informatics; spintronics, and so on. During the tenure of the present work, we have focused on two research aspects (i) Photovoltaic and (ii) thermoelectric. Therefore, certainly, the search for smart materials with potential applications in the fields of photovoltaic and thermoelectric is the main theme of this research work.

1.1 Photovoltaic material for energy conversion

To cope up with the energy crisis originated from rapid depletion of traditional energy sources and to sustain with rapidly increasing population the demand for electrical energy is increasing

day by day. The quality of life is poor when people are deprived of electricity. For day-to-day need, energy is required to sustain the supply of food, water, health, transportation, connectivity. In a broader respect industrial development and progress of civilization depend on adequate supply of energy. The energy consumption to the society rises to three times during the last 50 years. The nature of world energy consumption in Million tonnes oil equivalent (Mtoe \approx 42 PJ) and the corresponding available resources and consumption in India, China and US for the last 50 years have been plotted in Fig. 1.1(a). India has made substantial improvement in energy sectors in the recent years. It is noted that the primary consumption of energy is achieved via the resources of conventional fossil fuels viz., coal, oil and natural gas. With passage of time, the demand for energy is also increasing as can be viewed in Fig. 1.1(b). It is predicted that the energy consumption would increase by 28% by the end of year 2040. To meet the energy crisis, there is need of sustainable and ecofriendly energy sources. In this regard, photovoltaic technology is emerging candidate to fulfill the energy demands. It worthy to mentioned here that, photovoltaic technology is renewable and environment friendly which shows is tremendous to potential to convert solar into electricity.

Figure 1.1: (a) The trend for world energy consumption in Million tonnes oil equivalent (Mtoe \approx 42 PJ) along with the corresponding values for India, China, and the US for the last 50 years. (b) Energy generated from different sources for the year 2017 as utilized by different countries to meet their energy demands¹.

Over the years, scientist, researchers, and industries have collaborated to search the answer to the constant energy demand. In this scenario, solar energy has always attracted lots of attention. The important thing is that the solar light is natural, renewable and available everywhere. The concept of photovoltaic cell is to convert solar light into electricity. The light is nothing but electromagnetic waves emitted by sun and reaching onto the earth surface. It is important to mention that sun emitted all possible frequency. However, only fraction of its can reach the earth surface. The cause of energy loss is due to the absorption by the earth atmosphere. There are many absorbing agents namely ozone, water molecule, nitrogen and carbon dioxide. The AM1.5 spectra demonstrate the amount of light available for a solar cell which to be converted into electricity. This indicates that maximum intensity is located in the range visible spectrum, however to get maximum photovoltaic efficiency, the entire range of light spectrum should be converted.

As it is discussed that the photovoltaic technology can convert solar light into electricity for that we need semiconducting material having suitable electronic and optical properties. Depending upon the progress of the technology, it can be divided into different generations namely first generation, second and third generation photovoltaic cells. In first generation solar cell, we have crystalline solar cell. The important feature of this type of solar cell is that they have high carrier mobility and it is a mature technology. But problem with this type of solar cell is that they have high production cost and there is loss of photon energy. Then second-generation solar cell, we have amorphous silicon based solar cell, copper indium gallium selenide based solar cell, or cadmium telluride based solar cell. The advantage of this type of solar cell is having low production cost but low PCE makes them not suitable candidate. Lastly, we have third generation solar cell, for example perovskite solar cell, organic and sensitized solar cell. The important feature of such kind of solar cell is that they have low production cost with large PCE. However, short-term stability and toxic nature are the major drawback of such type of solar cell.

We have shown the progress of various type of solar cell in NREL data. It is observed that the multi-junction solar cell is having highest efficiency among all types of solar cell. The higher efficiency of such type of solar cell is because they have capability to absorb entire part of solar energy reaching the earth surface. But, the production process of such type of solar cell is complicated. Also, they are not cost effective which makes them not suitable. So, we have to look into other candidate having low cost, high PCE and stable. In this scenario, perovskite solar cell gains tremendous attention because of their suitable electronic properties and low cost. Also, their progress in terms of increment efficiency is tremendous. Still their PCE is smaller than multi-junction solar cell. This is due

to the fact that there is lack exploration of ideal perovskite material and optimization of PCE.

Figure 1.2: Progress of different types of solar cell in terms of efficiency obtained from National Renewable Energy Laboratory.

1.2 Characteristics of Photovoltaic Cells

The photovoltaic cell is comparable with cell with the difference is that it can do anything under dark condition [19]. There is a development of photovoltage when the light is falling on it. If the two terminals of the device are disconnected the created photovoltage is known as the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}). The electricity produced by the cell in the presence of light with the connection of two terminals is called short circuit current (I_{sc}). As the electricity produced by the solar device depends on the area of the surface of illuminated region, thus the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) can be replaces the short circuit current (I_{sc}).

In the absence of light, a photovoltaic cell can act as a diode (figure 1.3), with the difference in current in reverse bias ($V < 0$) compared to forward bias ($V >$

0). This rectifying behavior of photovoltaic cell in dark condition is shown below. In the presence of light the I(V) plots of the diode is getting changed by a factor which is proportional to the short circuit current.

Electrically, the photovoltaic cell can be compared with a electricity producer in parallel with a diode (figure 1.4). In the absence of diode, no photovoltage will be generated and the will be absence of photocurrent across the load .

Figure 1.4: Equivalent circuit of a photovoltaic cell.

The working range of a photovoltaic cell is from 0 to V_{oc} . Within this range the cell transport power which can be calculated as

$$P = JV \tag{1.1}$$

The largest value of P is defined as the maximum power point of the device, which can be possible at a voltage V_m with the corresponding current density J_m . We can define the new property of a photovoltaic cell that is called fill factor (FF) as:

$$FF = \frac{J_m V_m}{J_{sc} V_{oc}} \tag{1.2}$$

which demonstrate the "squareness" of the current density versus voltage plot.

The PCE (η) of a photovoltaic cell is defined as the ratio of maximum power point to that of incident light power density P :

$$\eta = \frac{J_m V_m}{P_s} \quad (1.3)$$

From the definition of FF in (1.3):

$$\eta = \frac{J_m V_m FF}{P_s} \quad (1.4)$$

The four quantities: J_{sc} , V_m , FF and η are the key parameters to understand the performance of a photovoltaic cell.

Thermoelectric Devices

The thermoelectric heat convertors are solid-state heat engines that can transform heat to electric voltage or vice-versa [19-22]. So, thermoelectric devices (TEDs) provide a proper and efficient technique to renovate waste heat. Thereby, these devices are at best to cope with the energy crisis. Moreover, such devices generate energy without harming the environment green energy, unlike fossil fuels. Besides this, TEDs are solid-state devices that have a long-life duration and need less maintenance. Electrons and holes act as "working fluids," which are long-lasting and don't need to be replenished. Moreover, unlike solar cells and hydrothermal power sources, TEDs can be installed in any environment.

Figure 1.5: Pictorial representation of thermoelectric module (a) Seebeck effect, (b) Peltier effect, (c) Thermoelectric modules connected in series.

The TEDs module has two semiconducting legs/blocks, doped alternatively with *p*-type and *n* type dopants [23]. This semiconducting couple is connected via metallic strips represented in Figure 1.5. The connections are designed in such a way that the blocks are in parallel for thermal conduction but series for electrical conduction. The electrons in *n*-type block move parallel to holes in the *p*-block. The electric current flows parallel to charge flow in *p*-type, whereas it flows antiparallel to charge flow in *n*-type. Therefore, the current that enters a metal strip from the *n* block exit the strip through the *p*-block. When the current is passed through the module, the top metal strip collects electrons from the *n*-type semiconductor, injects them into the valence-band holes of the *p*-type block. Thereby, lowering the electron's energy, as a result, energy is released and the top strips heat up. To create the outgoing holes, a bottom strip must take electrons from the valence band of a *p*-block. These electrons must be introduced into the conduction band of an *n*-block. Because this requires energy, the energy is provided by bottom strips. Therefore, when the current is passed, it functions as a heat pump, removing heat from the cold side and adding it to the hot side. The heat transported (Q) is directly proportional to the current passed (I), the

proportionality constant is the Peltier coefficient (P) i.e., $\dot{Q} = PI$. However, instead of passing current, when temperature difference (ΔT) is applied across the metallic strips, heating one side while keeping another side cold. Charge transport from higher temperature to lower temperature side, generating a voltage across the slabs. The voltage (ΔV) generated depends upon the difference of T between hot and cold sides. The constant of proportionality is the material's property defined as the thermopower, also known as thermoelectric power or Seebeck coefficient (S), $\Delta V = S\Delta T$. Many thermoelectric modules can be connected in series to form a Peltier cooler or thermoelectric power generator depending upon whether current is being passed or temperature gradient is applied. The power generator works reverse to Peltier cooler; however, their building block construction is the same.

1.4. Thermoelectric Figure of Merit

The limitation that back hits the wide range commercialization of TEDs is the low efficiency compared to mechanical engines, which needed to be resolved. The conversion rate of TEDs can be obtained from the ratio of output electrical power from the device to the input thermal power exploited during the progression given by [24];

$$\eta = \frac{T_h - T_c}{T_h} \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 + ZT} - 1}{\sqrt{1 + ZT} + \frac{T_c}{T_h}} \right] \quad (1.5)$$

T_h and T_c symbolize the temperature of hot and cold sides, respectively. The equation makes it clear that the efficiency is proportional to ZT. The figure of merit for a single leg at any temperature T can be obtained from Seebeck coefficient (S), electric conductivity (σ), and thermal conductivity (κ) of that leg [25];

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma T}{\kappa} \quad (1.6)$$

However, two legs n -type and p -type, with metallic inter connections are employed in TEDs. The total efficiency is therefore calculated by taking into account efficiencies of both blocks as well as interconnections thermal and electrical losses. Ignoring the losses, an imprecise estimate of the figure of merit (ZT) is [26].

$$ZT = \frac{(S_p - S_n)^2 T}{\left[(\rho_n \kappa_n)^{1/2} + (\rho_p \kappa_p)^{1/2} \right]^2} \quad (1.7)$$

S, ρ and κ symbolize Seebeck coefficient, resistivity, and thermal conductivity, respectively, while subscripts n and p are used to indicate n and p doped legs. Here ZT estimate the maximum reversibility of the thermodynamic process.

1.5 Problem with Thermoelectric Parameters

The thermoelectric parameters are coupled via mobility and carrier concentration. The behavior of the electronic band structure, particularly at the Fermi level, has a direct impact on transport properties. The desired thermoelectric material requires high thermopower like an insulator and a low resistivity like metal, however, this is practically difficult to achieve. The low bandgap degenerate semiconductors currently are at the sweet spot. As a result, such materials are on the lookout for thermoelectric technology. Mott relation can be used to describe the indirect relation of thermopower with other parameters [27].

$$S = \frac{8\pi^2 k_B^2}{3e\hbar^2} m^* T \left(\frac{\pi}{3n} \right)^{2/3} \quad (1.8)$$

k_B, \hbar, m^* , and n represent Boltzmann's constant, reduced Planck's constant, effective mass of carrier and number of carriers, respectively. The charge carriers in a leg should be of a single type (either p or n -type) as mixed types of carries

cancel out each other effects thereby reducing the generated potential. The Seebeck coefficient exhibit an inverse relationship with carrier concentration. Therefore, large thermopower can be attained against low carrier concentration but it would allow low electrical conductivity [27].

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho} = ne\mu \quad (1.9)$$

1.6 Approaches to Enhance the Figure of Merit

Attempts to increase S significantly reduce σ . Conversely, increasing σ would decrease S while increasing κ . Thus, it is beneficial to optimize thermoelectric parameters or much more decouple them somehow. With the advancement of nano-structuring, decoupling has been made possible. At present two approaches are mostly followed to enhance ZT: (i) Thermoelectric based on lower dimensionality - nano-structuring [28]; (ii) Identification of new bulk materials with low κ [29]. The nano-structuring is quite helpful in resolving the interdependency of thermoelectric parameters. The enhanced density of states due to the quantum confinement effect is more favorable to increase the thermopower without decreasing conductivity. Besides, scattering at interfaces can give us control of reducing κ .

Aside from nanotechnology, an innovative approach is being developed to discover advanced bulk cage structured materials with ultralow κ . Slack proposed phonon-glass electron-crystal approach that is phonons should perceive the material as a glass (with a high degree of phonon scattering, low κ_L), whilst electrons should perceive it as a crystal (with low scattering rate, high σ) [30]. Moreover, complicated cage structural materials with open crystallographic sites can act as a "host" to fillers, that are loosely bound with basic structural significantly scatter phonons thereby reduce κ_L - Rattling effect [31].

1.7 Lead-free halide double perovskites as photovoltaic and thermoelectric materials

Perovskites are ternary compounds named after Russian material scientist Lev Perovski came to light after the discovery of CaTiO_3 by Gustav Rose in the Ural Mountains, 1839 [32]. The "perovskite" name is generally applied to all those materials that possess the same stoichiometric ratio or similar structure to that of CaTiO_3 [32]. Thus, perovskites have a general stoichiometric formula ABX_3 . Almost every element in the periodic table can be fitted in the perovskite structure at one or the other site. A constituent is the largest cation in the configuration, belongs to the alkali, alkaline earth, or rare-earth group, ideally located within the dodecahedral symmetry of X anions. B is another cation coordinated by six X ions, this site is mostly occupied by transition or inner-transition metal. However, in certain cases, B cation can be even taken from s/p block elements. Perovskites family constitute two sub-classes (i) Oxide perovskites: X site is occupied by oxygen; (ii) Halide perovskites: X site is occupied by halogen member (F, Cl, Br, I). The perovskites are probably the best-studied family of materials, since their discovery [33]. The $A - X$ and $B - X$ bond lengths are in equilibrium, for the ideal perovskite ionic radii of constituents follow conditions: $(r_A + r_X) = \sqrt{2}(r_B + r_X)$ here r_i represent the ionic radii of the constituents. Correspondingly, the tolerance factor is defined as:

$$t = \frac{(r_A + r_X)}{\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_X)} \quad (1.11)$$

The degree of distortion present in perovskites can be predicted by how the geometric factor t deviates from the unity. When $0.9 < t < 1.0$, all atoms perfectly fit individual positions thereby result in an ideal cubic $\text{Pm}\bar{3}\text{m}$ structure. The rhombohedral or orthorhombic structures is formed for $0.71 < t < 0.9$ while

the hexagonal structure is stable for $1.0 < t < 1.05$. Different structures most possibly non-perovskite are formed for $t < 0.71$. The changeover from single perovskite to double perovskite halides changes the prototype structure from $Pm\bar{3}m$ to $Fm\bar{3}m$, shown in Fig. 2.1. The $Fm\bar{3}m$ structure of double perovskites halides consists of four interpenetrating fcc sublattices. The B and B' cations in ordered double perovskites occupy alternative sites (rock salt type structure) or even can be layer-wise ordered. In this study, we have focused only on rock-salt type structures. The BX_6 and $B'X_6$ octahedra form a corner-shared network, with inter-octahedra voids filled by the A cation as shown in Figure 1.6. However, like in the single perovskite halides, depending on the ionic radii and electronegativity of constituents, tilting of the octahedra takes place, which gives rise to lower symmetry structures. Thus, the double perovskite tolerance factor (t_{dp}) is commonly utilized to anticipate the structure of new members. The main difference concerning the single perovskite's halide tolerance factor is that in double perovskite halide case two bond distances (B-X and B' - X) needed to be taken into account. Consequently, the double perovskite tolerance factor t_{dp} can be defined as [34, 35]

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(r_A + r_X)}{(r_{BB'} + r_X)} \quad (1.12)$$

Here, $r_{BB'}$ represents average ionic radii of B and B' cations. The BX_6 and $B'X_6$ octahedra can expand / contract and tilt to adjust the ion-size ratios which are not optimum. Tilting in perovskites halide mostly happens when the A cation is too small for AX_{12} cavity. For small A, an empty space arises around it that needs to be filled up. Consequently, the BX_6 and $B'X_6$ octahedra rotate reduces the bond-distance mismatch. When t_{dp} is less than unity the B - X and B' - X bonds experience compression and the A-X bonds stretch. The structure alleviates these

stresses by allowing bending of BXB' bond angles from 180° to $(180^\circ - \theta)$. When $t_{dp} > 1$, B - X bonds are under tension whilst A - X bonds experience compression. In this situation, the BXB' bond angle remains 180° , but the B - X and B' - X bonds distort.

Figure 1.5 : (a) Crystal structure ABX_3 and (b) octahedral ordering of $A_2BB'X_6$ perovskites

A lot of research has been devoted to understanding the properties of perovskites and the physical phenomenon behind them. The recent research shows that halide perovskites have outstanding optoelectronic properties such as large dielectric constant, long carrier life-time, high carrier mobility, outstanding optoelectronic properties. However, they are unstable and have toxic nature which hindered their large-scale commercialization. Therefore, it is urgent to explore new compound which has identical electronic and optical properties as halide perovskite. Also, the explored material should be stable and have non-toxic nature. The chemical formula of lead-free halide double perovskite is $A_2BB'X_6$. The existence of

different transition elements cations at B -site and alkaline earth metal cation at A -site provide better flexibility and degree of freedom. By the proper choice of A and B site cation and halide anions X we can derive direct band gap of $A_2BB'X_6$ materials having band gap value in the range of 0.9 eV to 1.6 eV. It is worthy to mentioned here that if there perfect matching of electronic configuration of B site cations then there is a formation of direct E_g in lead-free halide double perovskite. Also, the band gap of lead-free halide double perovskite decreases if move from $X = F$ to $X = I$. The appropriate combination of A and B site cation and halide anions X can provide outshining optical properties of lead-free halide double perovskite which is suitable for photovoltaic technology. Also, It is worthy to mentioned here that many lead-free halide double perovskites small value of k with large σ due to their small band gap and presence of cation at the octahedral cavity. The small thermal conductivity along with huge σ gives rise to the figure of merit of lead-free halide close to unity.

1.1 Thesis organization

The present thesis is divided into the following chapters:

Chapter 1 gives an introduction about photovoltaic and thermoelectric energy conversion. This chapter starts with a discussion about the need for energy conversion materials and definition of photovoltaic materials. Also, we have discussed the significance of photovoltaic technology over non-renewable energy sources. Later, we have discussed about characteristics of solar cells. In addition to this, the PCE along with its relation to the material's properties is discussed. Next, we have defined the thermoelectric device and the efficiency of TEG, figure of merit, lead-free halide double perovskites materials and their properties. Thereafter, we have discussed about problem with thermoelectric parameters and

approach to enhance figure of merit. Finally, we have discussed about structural, optoelectronic and thermoelectric properties of $A_2BB'X_6$. Moreover, the importance of $A_2BB'X_6$ as photovoltaic and thermoelectric materials are discussed.

Chapter 2 provides a brief theory of the methods used in the thesis to study the electronic, phonon and transport properties of compounds. It starts with a description of DFT, then the Kohn-Sham equations and their self-consistent solution are briefly discussed. Next, the various XC functionals are discussed in subsection. The theory of semiclassical transport is given in next section. In the next section, we have discussed about phonon calculation. Then, the first-principles calculation techniques of phonon properties are summarized. In the last, the details SCAPS-1D simulation and its working steps are mentioned.

In Chapter 3, We have carried out details studies on $Rb_2Ag(Ga/In)Br_6$. The obtained band gap values show that they are outstanding material for green energy technology. Further studies revealed that they have outshining optoelectronic properties required for green energy technology. Moreover, huge electrical conductivity, ultra-low thermal conductivity and large value of figure of merit (ZT) tells that they are TE materials.

In Chapter 4, there is a systematic study on electronic, optical, structural, photovoltaic and thermoelectric properties of $Cs_2GeSnCl_6$ by using SCAPS-1D and DFT simulation. The obtained thermodynamic stability of $Cs_2GeSnCl_6$ is confirmed by its negative formation energy. The details of electronic property show the direct E_g nature of $Cs_2GeSnCl_6$ with a gap value of 1.01 eV (with mBJ + SOC). In addition, the predicted optical properties confirmed the excellent

conductivity and high absorption coefficient of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. Furthermore, a solar cell having the structure of ITO/ZnO/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /Au was made which shows a maximum power conversion efficiency of 18.74%. Moreover, the higher ZT value of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is coming from small k with large σ . Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is suitable for green energy technology.

In chapter 5, we have studied the magnetic and spin-based thermoelectric properties of K_2WX_6 [$\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$]. The spin-polarized band structure along with density of states shows show the half-metallic nature of both compounds. Further, the calculated spin based optical properties shows that the down channel of both compounds is having higher order of absorption coefficient and low reflectivity which tells that we can used them for high efficiency solar cell by polarizing in down channel direction. The thermoelectric parameters are calculated to examine the suitability in spin based Seebeck effect. The high σ , S, PF, ZT and low thermal along the spin down channel demonstrated that we can used them for high efficiency thermoelectricity by polarizing in down channel direction.

Chapter 6 summarizes the thesis, with a brief overview of the significant conclusions drawn and gives direction for future work.